

Studies of natrolite and its cation-exchanged and adsorbed derivatives with Co^{II} and liquor NH_3 and $\text{H}_2\text{S}^\dagger$

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Abstract : These studies are based on the investigation carried out on the cation exchange and adsorption behaviour of a natrolite which is natural zeolite collected from Sinner, Nasik (Maharashtra) as a geological specimen. Co^{II} -natrolite was prepared by treating a saturated aqueous Co^{II} -nitrate solution with natrolite by continuous shaking at 60 °C for maximum interaction. A portion of this exchanged derivative was then heated over a meker burner for several days in a platinum crucible. Both, the original and the preheated Co^{II} -natrolite samples were also interacted with gaseous H_2S and liqueor NH_3 to study their sorption capacity and preheating affects. All the derivatives and the original natrolite before and after heating were analyzed by XRD and FTIR.

Keywords : Natrolite, XRD, cation exchange, adsorption behaviour.

Introduction

All commercial applications of natrolite type zeolites make use of one or more of several physical or chemical properties, including ion exchange, adsorption and related molecular sieve properties^{1,2}. The exchangeable cations of a zeolite are only loosely bonded to the tetrahedral framework and can be removed or exchanged easily by washing with a strong solution of another ion. The ion exchange and adsorption properties have been well studied³⁻⁵.

In the present work a natural zeolite (natrolite) has been used to prepare its cation exchanged and adsorbed derivatives with Co^{II} and adsorbates like H_2S and liqueor NH_3 . The effect of heating on the new derivatives has been evaluated from XRD and FTIR studies. Co^{II} and the adsorbed species cause environmental hazards and their control can be possible by the cation exchange and adsorption processes with zeolites.

The aim of the present study is to test the suitability of such natural material as cation exchangers and adsorbates for H_2S and NH_3 which pose hazards both in the atmosphere and water needed to be controlled⁶.

Results and discussion

X-Ray studies : X-Ray diffraction data on natrolite and its interacted derivatives are shown in the Fig. 1(a-g) which reveals that Co^{II} -natrolite and its interacted derivatives are crystalline and orthorhombic (XRD data compared with 1996 JCPDS-International Center for Diffraction Data), the index of XRD data are shown in Table 1. The presence of aluminate tetrahedra in Co^{II} -natrolite and its interacted derivative framework is expected to cause an expansion or contraction in lattice.

The diffraction data also show reduction in the number of peaks (Fig. 1(e-g)) which may be due to the change of space group. Residual Co^{II} -natrolite and its interacted derivatives are crystalline. So the material obtained by heating has good stability and good crystallinity.

The X-ray data of residual derivatives show a shift of diffraction peaks to higher 2θ values as compared to Co^{II} -natrolite and its interacted derivatives, which is consistent with more siliceous framework.

FTIR :

The FTIR spectral data of Co^{II} -natrolite and its inter-

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Note

Table 1. XRD data of natural natrolite and its various products before heating

XRD of natural natrolite + Co + stirred :			
(d) Å	h	k	l
6.3369	2	2	0
4.6043	4	0	0
4.4944	1	3	1
4.2669	3	1	1
4.0455	4	2	0
3.1571	5	1	1
3.1116	0	2	2
2.8697	3	5	1
2.8331	5	3	1
2.5036	1	7	1
2.1755	6	6	0
2.1755	6	2	2
1.7965	3	5	3
1.7965	7	7	1
1.7312	4	10	0
1.5988	10	0	2
1.5988	2	2	4
1.5794	7	9	1
XRD of natural natrolite + Co + NH ₃ + stirred :			
6.6204	2	2	0
6.4926	2	2	0
5.7692	1	1	1
4.6763	0	4	0
4.5700	4	0	0
4.5639	4	0	0
4.3285	3	1	1
4.1625	2	4	0
4.1190	4	2	0
3.2778	4	4	0
3.1301	0	2	2
2.9084	6	2	0
2.8646	3	5	1
2.6642	2	4	2
2.1931	2	6	2
2.1789	6	6	0
2.1789	6	2	2
1.8679	2	8	2
1.7461	8	4	2
XRD of natural natrolite + Co + H ₂ S + stirred :			
6.3249	4	4	2
5.6467	8	0	0
4.5407	4	0	0
4.2875	3	1	1
3.1346	5	1	1
2.8798	3	5	1
2.8798	3	5	1
2.8342	5	3	1
2.4106	7	1	1
2.2633	7	3	1
2.2633	6	2	2
2.0072	6	4	2
1.5729	9	7	1
1.5700	9	7	1

Table 2. XRD data of natural natrolite and its various products after heating

XRD of natural natrolite + Co + stirred + heat :			
(d) Å	h	k	l
5.4942	1	1	1
4.9468	0	4	0
3.9656	4	2	0
3.6538	3	3	1
3.1761	5	1	1
3.1560	5	1	1
2.8341	5	3	1
2.6352	2	4	2
2.3924	7	1	1
2.1298	1	1	3
1.9476	9	1	1
1.8229	2	10	0
1.7602	4	8	2
XRD of natural natrolite + Co + NH ₃ + stirred + heat :			
6.1212	2	2	0
5.7481	1	1	1
4.8966	0	4	0
3.9276	4	2	0
3.6837	3	3	1
3.3753	4	4	0
3.1719	5	1	1
2.6356	2	4	2
2.4512	1	7	1
2.0680	8	4	0
1.8242	2	10	0
XRD of natural natrolite + Co + H ₂ S + stirred + heat :			
6.5020	2	2	0
5.6312	1	1	1
4.9963	0	4	0
3.9064	4	2	0
3.6548	3	3	1
3.1540	5	1	1
2.9252	2	2	2
2.6098	2	4	2
2.4595	1	7	1
2.0292	6	4	2
1.8912	1	5	3
1.8184	2	10	0
1.7657	4	8	2
1.7254	4	10	0
1.5735	10	6	0

acted derivatives with H₂S and NH₃ are reproduced in Table 3. Co^{II}-natrolite derivative gives bands at 3567 to 3690 and 1636 to 1698 cm⁻¹ which are mainly due to the stretching and bending vibrations of water respectively : The weak intensity band at 3839 to 3904 cm⁻¹ in H₂S

Fig. 1. XRD spectra of natural natrolite and its various products before heating and after heating.

interacted Co^{II} -natrolite can be attributed to silanol bands (Si-OH modes). The band at 3735 and 3751 cm^{-1} in natrolite is inductive of the Al-OH modes. Adsorption of H_2S on Co^{II} -natrolite produces a medium intensity bands at 1457, 1473 cm^{-1} due to S-H linkage or sulphur containing species like sulphate, sulphite etc. and spectra of Co^{II} -exchanged natrolites always show a peak at 559 cm^{-1} which can be assigned to Co^{II} -O or Co^{II} -S or something similar besides T-O bending vibration where T = (Si, Al) $_4\text{O}$. The band at around 2360 cm^{-1} indicates the S-H

stretching vibration. Ammonia adsorbed by Co^{II} -natrolite produces the characteristic FTIR band at 1458 cm^{-1} for H-N-H bending vibration. 3397, 3398 and 1507, 1522, 1541, 1559 cm^{-1} may be assigned to N-H stretching.

FTIR data of preheated residue of Co^{II} -natrolite and its interacted derivatives are shown in Table 4. The derivatives show loss of number of peaks due to heating or changed in space group. They show spectra of O-H bands due to loss of physically adsorbed water molecules. The medium intensity band at 3735 cm^{-1} in all the samples.

Note

Table 3. Parameters pertaining to Co^{II}-natrolite before heating

Assignment	Co ^{II} -natrolite (cm ⁻¹)	NH ₃ interacted Co ^{II} -natrolite (cm ⁻¹)	H ₂ S interacted Co ^{II} -natrolite (cm ⁻¹)
v(OH)	3567, 3587	3397, 3398	3397
δ(H-OH)	1636, 1647, 1653, 1670, 1684, 1698	1670	1636
Pore opening	420	418	418
δ(T.O.)	466-480	497	459
Double ring	569-594	594-632	545, 594
v _{sym} (T.O.) internal linkage	721	697	-
v _{sym} (T.O.) external linkage	751	-	-
v _{asym} (T.O.) internal linkage	1103	-	-
v _{asym} (T.O.) external linkage	932, 956, 990	989	1023
δd(NH ₄ ⁺)	-	1458	-
v(NH ₄ ⁺)	-	2361	-
H ₂ S physical	-	-	1457, 1473
v(S-H)	-	-	2360
v(Si-OH) modes	3904	Absent	3840, 3850, 3904
v(Al-OH) modes	3735	3735	3751

Table 4. Parameters pertaining to Co^{II}-natrolite after heating

Assignment	Co ^{II} -natrolite (cm ⁻¹)	NH ₃ interacted Co ^{II} -natrolite (cm ⁻¹)	H ₂ S interacted Co ^{II} -natrolite (cm ⁻¹)
v(OH)	3518, 3583, 3584	3396, 3397	3465
δ(H-OH)	1635, 1636, 1652, 1683	1668	1634
Pore opening	408-418	439-476	480
δ (T.O.)	456-469	488	449
Double ring	569	594	540
v _{sym} (T.O.) internal linkage	677	675	711
v _{sym} (T.O.) external linkage	-	-	-
v _{asym} (T.O.) internal linkage	930, 951, 988	988	1022
v _{asym} (T.O.) external linkage	1105	-	-
δd(NH ₄ ⁺)	-	1457	-
v(NH ₄ ⁺)	-	2360	-
H ₂ S physical	-	-	-
v(S-H)	-	-	-
v(Si-OH) modes	Absent	3801, 3820, 3838, 3853	3839, 3854
v(Al-OH) modes	Absent	3711, 3735, 3751	-

The intensity band 3820 cm⁻¹ in samples are Si-OH modes. The H₂S interacted preheated Co^{II}-zeolite exhibits no band for physically adsorbed H₂S, only a weak band for OH stretching. NH₃ interacted derivative shows peaks 1457 and 3396, 3397 cm⁻¹ due to H-N-H stretching vibration and the T-O stretching band at around 1150 cm⁻¹ 7-9.

Experimental

Naturally occurring zeolite (natrolite) as a geological specimen collected from Sinner, Nasik (Maharashtra) was

powdered after cleaning, washing and grinding to very fine white particles. Co^{II}-exchanged derivative of natural zeolite was prepared by treating 20 g of this powdered natrolite with 100 mL saturated aqueous solution of cobalt nitrate and shaken for 15 days. Reactants were warmed in an electrically operated water bath at 60 °C for maximum interaction. After 15 days the solid natrolite was filtered and washed before air drying. A bluish Co^{II}-exchanged derivative was obtained. One part of this sample was continuously heated over a meker burner for

10 h in platinum crucible. A dull Co^{II} bluish derivative was obtained. Adsorbed derivative were prepared by the procedure described in the literature¹⁰⁻¹².

XRD data were obtained between 2 θ angles of 10 to 60° and the scanning rate were 3° with the help of Rigaku D/max-2200, X-ray diffractometer measurements were made using 40 kV/20 mA, Cu K α 1, wavelength 1.54 Å. FTIR spectra were recorded on a ABB FTLA-2000 spectrophotometer.

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